

KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE AND BORROWED WORDS

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Annotation: This article talks about the history of borrowed words in the Karakalpak language taken from other languages. There are given some extralinguistic factors with explanations and examples.

Key words: Karakalpak language, structure, borrowed words, communication, linguistic.

We all know that language is one of the subjects that have been learned since ancient times, and that it provides the most valuable information about language, its nature, structure, and units. Indeed, language acts as a special means of communication in society. Language is considered to be a unique phenomenon in the nature of a tangible object of learning, which analyzes various points of view and develops in the course of a person's life. In particular, there is a special place for self-words. Borrowed words in the vocabulary of the Karakalpak language are often used in each subject and are known for most people.

That is why, at the end of the 20th century, the active learning of pragmatic markers of personal words by the representatives of various cultures began to take place, and while defining them, scientists created the concept of each type. In language education, the words used in language education are separated from the study in all directions, and the words that are used in communication and their learning are one of the most relevant topics.

No matter how specific and closed the language is, in the course of modern globalization it is prone to constant changes. This, first of all, is related to the topic of lexicology, which is directly related to the internal and external radiation of the language. The human world uses words to name material objects in the process of close communication between people, exchange of new technologies, ideas and others. In this way, cultures and languages are connected and influenced by each other [1].

A. A. Reformatsky "there is not a single language in the world whose vocabulary is limited only to the original words. Each language has its own words and foreign language units. In different languages and in different periods of their development, it may not be the words of this language, but different types [2].

The borrowed words adapt to the norms of the language and come from the database of those new words. In this case, the received language has the strongest influence on the words.

Language is constantly changing, like a living organism in action. That's why N. S. Valgina notes that "diachrony is defined and replaced by the replacement of one language sign by others, synchronically - by struggle with variants, joint creation and demand for normality" [3]. And M.G. Dakokhova suggests that "Dictionary is a "barometer" of social changes and dynamics of linguistic community organizations" [4].

In the education of the Russian language, several students have carried out research work on self-words. In particular, F.R.Fathullina [5], I.Krein [6], D.S.Lotte [7], O.S.Axmanova [8], S.I.Bahtina [9], M.N.Volodina [10], N.V.Vaganova [11], and the others tried to open the relevance to the different subjects.

F.R.Fathullina, in her dissertation, she takes into account the differences in the development of vocabulary in the present era and divides the language into extralinguistic factors [5]:

1. **Scientific and technical revolution.** This factor is related to the significant progress and rapid development of modern science and technology. As an example, we can mention a large number of imported technical devices: *computers, DVD players, music centers, mobile phones, flashcards* and many other devices. The procedure for using purely technical terms is written in foreign languages (in particular, in English), which directly leads to the complete adaptation of the lexical units of the English language. When we talk about technical growth, we should also mention that global computerization is emerging in society at the present time. In fact, computers are used in every aspect of our life, almost in every home. For that reason, the computer vocabulary is widely used not only in special institutions, but also in all communication tools.

2. **The increase in interest in the English language and the increase in the number of users.** The introduction of science and technology into our society has increased the demand for it. As for learning a foreign language among the people, the demand for the English language is growing day by day. The introduction of new equipment and terms of technical equipment into the Karakalpak language creates

mutual understanding between the speakers. As a result of increasing interest in the English language, gay words of the English language are being used in the Karakalpak language without translation among young people.

3. historical connections of the people and clear forms of bilingualism. The analysis of acquisition should start with the study of people who speak two languages.

Self-words are a type of linguistic relations that are separated from the pronunciation of a large number or a small number of self-contained units, which are characteristic of both monolingual and bilingual.

4. the development of the means of victory. The expansion of oral words over manuscripts and the increase of people's opportunities to receive information has become one of the socio-political realities in our society today. The prompt action of social media has created opportunities for its readers and listeners to see the world through television, radio, magazines, and newspapers, which are broadcast and broadcast every day, every month, and every week. This victory caused a large number of international terms to appear in our media society.

5. Social honor of foreign language pronouns. At the present time, the words themselves have become the reason for the emergence of linguistic fashion. Animation, briefing, rating, security, and many other borrowed words that came from the Russian language and other foreign languages based on the Russian language can be examples.

I. Crane, one of the foreign scholars, expresses his opinion about borrowed words as follows: "Every word from another language included in the dictionaries can be counted as a borrowed word" [12].

Russian scientist V.I.Maksimov in his new dictionary entitled "Slovar perestroiki", published in 1992, he takes as his main goal to get acquainted with the meaning and word formations, which he calls the reality and concepts that appeared in our literary language during the years of reconstruction (1985-1992). In the work of this dictionary, we include the words *stock*, *shareholder*, *alternative*, *apparatus*, *barter* and many others that entered the Karakalpak language while preserving their lexical and semantic meanings [13].

In 1993, The dictionary "Short dictionary of modern concepts and terms" published under the editorship of V.A.Makarenko is the first example of a short dictionary of frequently used lexical units, in particular, it shows the innovations of languages that are the main image of the social character [14].

D.S. Lotte examines borrowed words as words transferred from one language to another, coming into continuous contact with social life and the emergence of all kinds of cultures [15].

O.S. Akhmanova gives the following definition of self-words in her dictionary of linguistic terms.

1. The last difference is the access to the lexical background of other languages in order to reveal the concept in the explanation of the previously unknown subjects (later these concepts and subjects themselves become known to the people who speak that language, the corresponding words become known due to the contact with the people of the adopted languages).

2. As a result of adaptation, words that entered this language, word-making affixes and constructions were included.

Vocabulary is one of the most important issues in language education, which is studied from all aspects. Determining systematic relationships in the lexicon is a very topical issue in today's advanced age, due to the rich materials collected in the technology domain. In this lexical editor, systematicity is determined by examining words that belong to various thematic and lexical-semantic groups.

Although the lexical system of the language, compared to other systems of the language, tends to change under the influence of the changes that have occurred in society, there are stable subsystems (subsystems) in the work of this system, which remain unchanged for several generations, and different subsystems are caused by changes in socio-economic formations. will be updated.

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INTEGRATION OF SCIENCES IN EDUCATION, INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS IN CHEMISTRY AND OTHER DISCIPLINES

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Abstract: This article explores the integration of sciences in education, focusing on the interdisciplinary connections in chemistry and other related disciplines. It highlights the importance of integrating various scientific fields to foster a holistic understanding of complex phenomena. The paper discusses the benefits of interdisciplinary approaches in education, such as promoting critical thinking, enhancing problem-solving skills, and fostering a deeper appreciation for the interconnectedness of scientific disciplines. Examples of integrated lessons and projects are provided to illustrate the practical application of interdisciplinary concepts in the classroom. Overall, the paper emphasizes the significance of interdisciplinary connections in enriching the educational experience and preparing students for future scientific endeavors.

Key words: Integration, interdisciplinary connections, chemistry, mathematics, interdisciplinary tasks, problem-solving tasks, skills development, scientific worldview, activation of thinking, cognitive interest, spatial representations, logical thinking, subject knowledge, skills, acquisition of new ways of activity.

Introduction

Currently, the issue of the quality of education has become one of the priorities. Alongside developing ways to optimize the learning process as a whole, there is a growing importance placed on researching the outcomes of this process. These outcomes should include key competencies. This means that the task of modern schooling is to develop in graduates the ability to independently create new knowledge and new ways of working, to perform a wide variety of cognitive tasks. The study of chemistry allows students to understand the essence of chemical processes occurring around us. To develop an interest in the subject, students need to be active participants in the learning process, not passive listeners. Cognitive activity is a socially significant quality of a personality; it is formed in organized and regulated educational activities